

PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF WOMEN'S SOCIAL PROTECTION BASED ON GENDER EQUALITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article strengthens the sociodiscursive and empirical study of this problem due to the fact that the problem of social protection of women in all countries of the world has become urgent global problem. This is explained, on the one hand, by the increased general need of women to improve their socio-political status and role, and on the other hand, by the fact that the position of women in the process of sustainable development is steadily increasing.

ФИЛОСОФИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ ЖЕНЩИН НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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ABSTRACT

В статье усиливается социодискурсивное и эмпирическое исследование данной проблемы в связи с тем, что проблема социальной защиты женщин во всех странах мира стала актуальной проблемой. Это объясняется, с одной стороны, повышенной общей потребностью женщин в повышении их социально-политического статуса и роли, а с другой-тем, что положение женщин в процессе устойчивого развития неуклонно растет.

O'ZBEKISTONDA GENDER TENGLIKNI TA'MINLASH ASOSIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNI IJTIMOYIY HIMOYA QILISHNING FALSAFIY JIHLTLARI

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ABSTRACT

Maqolada dunyoning barcha mamlakatlarida xotin-qizlarni ijtimoiy himoya qilish masalasi dolzarb global muammoga

KEYWORDS

Gender tenglik, ijtimoiy
himoya, global
muammo, tazyiq, zo'ravonlik,
oila institutlari, tahlil.

aylanganligi sababli mazkur muammoni sotsio-diskursiv va empirik tadqiq etish kuchaymoqda. Bu bir tomondan, ayollarning ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'rni va ro'lining ortishiga bo'lgan jamiyat ehtiyojining kuchayganligi bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan, barqaror taraqqiy etish jarayonida xotin-qizlarning mavqei tobora yuksalayotganligi bilan izohlanadi.

Introduction

4.2 of the strategy of Action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The priorities set out in the paragraph "improving the social protection and health system of the population, increasing the socio-political activity of women", in particular, social protection of women, ensuring gender equality, increasing participation in public administration, providing material, psychological, medical assistance to women in critical situations, providing them with housing and employment, strengthening family values, as a result of the work carried out on ensuring the stability of the spiritual environment in the family, the issue of social protection of women has reached a new level. The founder of a large-scale innovative activity and creativity, creative movement towards the creation of a new Uzbekistan, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted: "We will take work on the support of women and young people to a new level this year."²

Results and discussion

According to the 26th fashion of the Constitution of the new taxrire, human honor and dignity are inconclusive. The fact that nothing can serve as a basis for their discrimination is a sign that torture, violence, other shameless, inhuman or degrading treatment of human dignity cannot be punished, and medical and scientific experiments cannot be carried out without her consent in hechkim are established in our national legislation, which prohibits not only women, but also every person from freshness and violence.

This is prohibited from hiring, firing and reducing their wages for women due to their pregnancy or having a child in accordance with the third part of Article 42 of the constitution³ another concern aimed at protecting the rights and interests of women in our country.

In order to regulate relations in the field of protection of women from all forms of harassment and violence, on September 2, 2019, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "protection of women from harassment and violence " 4 " was adopted, according to which violence refers to their life, health, sexual or economic influence on women by threatening them with the use of measures of, a tariff is issued as a nonviolent act or inaction that encroaches on dignity and other rights and freedoms protected by law, as well as a separate tariff is issued for each type of violence, which:

Sexuality refers to a form of violence against women that encroaches on sexual inviolability and sexual freedom by committing acts of a sexual nature without their consent, as well as the use of violence or the threat of the use of violence, or the coercion of sex with a third party by committing immoral acts against minors of the female gender.

Physical violence refers to a form of violence that encroaches on the lives, health, freedom of women and other rights and freedoms protected by law, by threatening to inflict bodily

injuries of varying degrees of severity on women, to put them at risk, not to provide assistance to a person whose life is at risk, to commit other offenses of a violent nature, to

and mental violence is a form of violence expressed in other actions aimed at insulting, slandering, threatening women, belittling their honor, dignity, as well as limiting their desire, including control in the reproductive sphere, harassment and violence can be understood as an act or inaction that causes anxiety for their own safety in the victim, leads to inability to defend themselves or harms their mental health. Also in this law is such a form of violence that it is admitted is economic violence.

Economic violence refers to women we will be able to understand movement or inaction, which will lead to a form of violence carried out in marriage, workplaces and other places, limiting the right of wives to provide for normal living and maturation with food, housing and other necessary conditions, the right to property, the right to education and the right to work.

Development and implementation of gender policies, state programs and strategies in the field of protection of women from harassment and violence, creating an atmosphere of intolerance to harassment and violence against women in society, ensuring that women's rights, freedoms and legitimate interests are protected from harassment and violence, preventing harassment and violence against women, in order to identify them, create effective organizational and legal mechanisms to put an end to them, take measures to eliminate the causes and conditions that lead to the occurrence of harassment and violence against women, prevent harassment and violence against public bodies, citizens themselves it is defined as ensuring the cooperation of governing bodies, NGOs and other institutions of civil society. Also in this law, the vacuoles of state bodies related to the protection of women from taiziq and violence are prescribed to these vacuole state bodies of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, local government bodies, internal affairs bodies, labor bodies, state educational authorities, health system management bodies, family and women's committee under the Ministry of poverty reduction and employment, self-government bodies of citizens, these include NGOs and other institutions of civil society.

Conclusion

This article was published by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to support the conduct of sociological research by the state on February 22, 2019 PF-5667, February 18, 2020 PF-5938 "on measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood Institute and bring the system of working with family and women to a new level, Decrees of February 2, 2018 PF-5325 "on measures to radically improve the activities of women in the field of support and strengthening the Family Institute", December 22, 2017, Appeals to the Supreme Assembly of December 28, 2018 and January 25, 2020, resolution of March 7, 2019 PQ-4235 on measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurial activities, resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 11, 2019 "on additional measures to strengthen the social protection of orphans and children deprived of their parents " – Resolution No. 4185, No. 561 "on the protection of women from harassment and violence" of September 2, 2019, Law No. 562 "on equal rights and guarantees of opportunities for women and men" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2018 "on women in a difficult social situation, women with disabilities,, CM-285 on

approval of the regulation on the procedure for providing affordable housing to mothers who are raising their children in an incomplete family and need to improve housing conditions” and serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks set out in other meiori-legal documents on the topic.

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